

Practice Abstract no. 40

Improving data literacy and citizen empowerment across the food system

The #Data4Food Cluster comprising the [DRG4Food](#), [FOODITY](#), [FoodDataQuest](#), and [SOSFood](#) projects organised a joint workshop in June 2025 to discuss challenges, enablers, and gains related to data sharing and AI-driven solutions for sustainable food systems. Two breakout room sessions explored perspectives from both consumers/citizens and industry/food system actors on data sharing and AI in food systems.

Building on the findings of the workshop and breakout room sessions, the following recommendation and driving actions was proposed:

Recommendation: Improve general data literacy and citizen empowerment across the food system.

Proposed Actions:

- 1. Develop targeted education programmes:** Following the implementation of specific and well-developed legislation, tailored educational programs should be developed and delivered to various audiences, including consumers, farmers, and SMEs. These should focus on crucial topics such as data privacy, data rights, and the advantages of data-driven solutions. It is particularly important for citizens and consumers that these programmes be provided early on. Young people are increasingly using various digital devices and often share personal information without fully understanding the potential consequences of their actions.
- 2. Promote best practices for data quality:** Aligned with Recommendation 1, it is important to educate stakeholders on the importance of accurate and reliable data, and to provide guidelines for data validation and quality control.
- 3. Educate on the value of AI and address the AI trust deficit:** AI is becoming an unavoidable disruptive technology. The effectiveness, reliability, and capability of AI solutions are directly dependent on the quality of the data they use. To foster adoption, stakeholders must be educated on the value and opportunities of AI through clear communication and demonstrations of tangible benefits, while simultaneously addressing and respecting existing trust concerns. Although challenges and risks are associated with the uncontrolled use of AI, these can be mitigated through knowledgeable and moderate application of the technology.

The aforementioned information is available and further detailed in the joint report developed by the #Data4Food Cluster "What Helps and What Hurts When Sharing Data for Sustainable Food Solutions."

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